

THE ESA GEOLOGICAL ASTRONAUT TRAINING PROGRAM PANGAEA: PREPARING FOR THE MOON AT THE RIES CRATER, GERMANY. H. Hiesinger¹, C. H. van der Bogert¹, F. Sauro^{2,3}, M. Massironi⁴, R. Pozzobon³, N. Mangold⁵, Kåre Kullerud⁶, J.M Frias⁷, C. Cockell⁸, S. J. Payler², L. Bessone²:
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Introduction: PANGAEA (Planetary Analogue Geological and Astrobiological Exercise for Astronauts) is a field training course of the European Space Agency (ESA) that seeks to address the topics of geological and astrobiological planetary exploration [1, 2]. Starting in 2016, PANGAEA so far involved 16 astronauts from ESA, NASA, JAXA, and Roscosmos, as well as an additional 5 non-astronaut trainees including space engineers and EVA and operations specialists (Fig. 1). The goal of the program is to geologically train and prepare astronauts for future exploration of the lunar and Martian surfaces to maximize the scientific return from such human missions.

Motivation: Astronaut activities on space stations (e.g. MIR, ISS) are commonly heavily pre-planned and directed from ground control. However, in an explorational environment, such an approach does not capitalize enough on the significant situational awareness of an astronaut on the ground, which is critical for making rapid scientific decisions. A lesson learned from the Apollo missions is that given the preciousness of EVA time, astronauts

should be capable of making their own exploration-driven decisions, with assistance from ground only when needed. With PANGAEA, we intend to teach astronauts essential theoretical knowledge and practical skills necessary for making such decisions and to prepare them for more detailed follow-on training on the specific geology of selected landing sites. Hence, with PANGAEA, we help lay the groundwork to enable astronauts to understand fundamental geologic processes relevant for their work on the lunar and Martian surfaces, including volcanic, tectonic and impact processes and their resulting products and timing. During the training we also focus on skills that are relevant for future planetary missions, including scientific observations and decision-making, working and communicating with a remote team of science and engineering experts, as well as documenting observations and samples accurately.

The Moon and Mars: PANGAEA focuses primarily on the Moon and Mars as they are the most relevant planetary objects for human exploration in the foreseeable future. In fact, several space nations are working on executing plans for a lunar station that would offer astronauts shelter for long-term stays on the Moon. Although many experiments will probably be executed within this habitat, the exploration and geologic study of the vicinity will play a major role during such long-lasting visits. This requires solid geoscientific field training of the astronauts to maximize scientific return and it is well advised to begin preparations and training early.

Program: PANGAEA tries to accomplish these goals by offering a well-balanced training program consisting of lectures and exercises in classrooms and fieldwork to develop independent field skills in analogue geological environments. In its latest version, PANGAEA comprises about 51 hours of classroom lectures, 25 hours of practical exercises, and 60 hours of field trips and traverses, all offered within 3-4 weeks [2]. The classroom lectures and exercises take place at the respective field sites and cover topics that are best illustrated by different analogue sites. Four European sites were selected to provide broad geological training: 1) the Permian terrains of the Dolomites (Italy) for teaching fundamentals of geology and the geology of Mars; 2) the Ries crater in Germany for impact cratering processes and lithologies on the Moon and Mars, 3) the island of Lanzarote in the Canary archipelago for volcanism

PANGAEA 2016											
PANGAEA 2022											

Fig. 1: Participating astronauts and agencies of PANGAEA [2]

on Earth, the Moon, and Mars, and 4) the Flakstadøy intrusive complex on the Lofoten Islands, as an analogue to the lunar primary crust. The geologic complexity of the analogue sites and of the requested tasks become increasingly challenging for the astronauts as the course continues.

Ries Crater, Germany: Aspects of lunar geology are taught at the Ries crater in Germany, which was also a training site for the Apollo 14 and 17 astronauts. The classroom activities, which include lectures about impact cratering, volcanic, and tectonic processes, are accompanied by visits to relevant outcrops to introduce astronauts to the lithologies associated with an impact crater. Discussions about the mechanisms of ejecta emplacement, megablock movement along the crater wall, crater floor rebound and the formation of a central ring, and geophysical

data provide astronauts with hands on knowledge of cratering processes. While in Nördlingen, the astronauts also learn how to construct a basic geomorphological map using Lunar Orbiter images, which feeds into their understanding of geospatial mission planning materials.

Philosophy: Starting with relatively simple stratigraphic observations in the Dolomites and an introduction to minerals, rocks, and basic geologic concepts, the astronauts are requested to play more and more active roles as the course proceeds, culminating in the development and execution of traverses, practicing sampling and sample handling, and detailed reporting to the “back-room” scientists. It is the close temporal proximity of field work and relevant lectures/exercises that help astronauts in applying their theoretical classroom knowledge in the field. Tilting the course content towards practical, implementable knowledge over pure theory has been a key asset. In particular, giving the astronauts the possibility to actively engage in scientific problems, rather than simply executing prescribed procedures, prepares them well for becoming the main protagonists of possible discoveries and scientific advances once they are on the lunar/martian surface [3]. These are just a few benefits that PANGAEA provides which makes it highly valued by the astronauts.

Evolution: Over the course of the years, PANGAEA has been constantly improved and updated to reflect the latest knowledge in planetary sciences. Increasingly, we have also added the use of modern analytical tools to aid astronauts with sample selection and the general characterization of a given area. For example, ESA developed an electronic field book for documentation of findings that allows astronauts to collect images, notes, spectra, and other scientific data [4]. Each PANGAEA activity and instructor are constantly evaluated by the participants and this feedback is taken into account to further improve the course. Once future missions to the Moon are fully planned, additional adjustments will be made to tailor PANGAEA to ensure it continues to provide a highly relevant and valuable training experience.

Conclusions: In summary, PANGAEA offers valuable contributions to astronaut lunar geology training at the Ries Crater, Germany, representing an asset that ESA offers to other space agencies.

References: [1] Sauro et al. (2023) Acta Astron. 204; [2] Sauro et al. (2024) IAC-24-B3,IP,10,x86963; [3] Hodges and Schmitt (2011) Geol. Soc. Am. Spec. Paper 483. [4] Turchi et al. (2021) Planet. Space Sci. 197.

Fig. 2: Examples of analogue sites in PANGAEA [2].